

Women in Politics

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Abstract

Women the term unanimously means the powerful and the strongest gender of the society. Women play a significant role in family and in society. She as a multitasking human being balances both her family and her professional life. The age old society strictly followed the deep rooted patriarchal system which restricted women to step out of their home environment. But as the society tends to change, women realised the urge for gender equality and started to play an inevitable role in all fields of the profession, which led to the emergence of concept named women empowerment and emancipation. Even though women achieved success in different professional fields, when it comes under the banner of politics they are excluded. Women are politically excluded and even woman hesitate to choose politics as their profession. Women, who taste the fruit of success in many professions, still taste bitterness in politics. This theoretical paper aims to throw light on the political exclusion of women. The paper focuses on the challenges for women when they choose politics as their profession. This paper tries to accumulate the reasons for women's hesitation towards politics. But still few powerful women politicians are effectively performing in India. This theoretical paper also symbolizes those significant women in politics.

Introduction

“A Better Democracy is a Democracy Where Women Do not
Only have the Rights to Vote and to Elect But to be Elected”

- Michelle Bachelet

India is the oldest civilisation with world's largest democracy. The population of women in India is fair equal to that of men population. Women are the most strongest and the powerful gender of the society. But as of 2017 statistics India ranks at 127th place in Gender Inequality Index. A women being a women has to play many significant roles in her family and also in the society. She being a daughter, wife, mother, grandmother plays central role in her family and as a professional she engages in her work life too. Tracing the age old history women underwent exclusion in the name of gender. They were excluded and dominated by the men stating that they are physically and mentally inferior to them. The deep rooted patriarchal society restricted women growth and their development. Women themselves felt that they are inferior to men and started to work for the whims and fancies of men and they thought that their full time duty is to take care of their family. As the society tends to change, many improvements took place in the status of women. Many women

came out of their long lived kitchen and stepped out of their homes. They realised the true sense of their capacities, skills and successfully utilised them to acquire not only easy jobs but also to take part in many adventures risky jobs. The concept of women empowerment bear the fruit and it brought out a positive change in the status and position of women in the society. Women demanded an egalitarian society and they proved that they are no more inferior to men. The amendments made to the Indian constitution regarding women reservation added fuel to the empowerment concept.

Women in Politics

Abraham Lincoln defines democracy as “FOR THE PEOPLE, OF THE PEOPLE, BY THE PEOPLE”. The term democracy means equality for both men and women in all walks of life and in all fields of work. United Nations states that “women constitute world’s largest excluded category”. The exclusion of women covers all the subsystem of the society. As women were considered as the vulnerable population they were socially, economically, culturally and politically excluded. But after women emancipation even though they were included on many grounds still a wide disparity prevails on the grounds of politics and even today women experience political exclusion. Even though the law provides a scope for general participation of women in politics, right to vote, right to contest in elections etc women are still denying to choose politics as their main stream profession.

The government of India tried hard to eliminate the political exclusion of women. In order to do so, they formulated enormous laws and even amended the constitution to ensure women’s participation in politics. Since independence many laws were formulated to safeguard the rights of women community. The fundamental rights of our constitution provide right for equality and liberty. It prohibits discrimination based on sex, religion, caste, class etc. The 73rd and 74th constitutional amendments in 1993 was deliberately formed to indulge women in politics and in decision making process at the grass root level by reserving one third of the seats for women all over the country. The Panchayati Raj Institution (PRI) furnished a greater scope for women representation, participation in politics. PRIs not only provided an impact in the development of rural areas but it also broke the myths that women are incapable to decide right things and they are submissive to men. The Women Reservation Bill was firstly initiated in the year 1996 and the 81st amendment of this bill granted 33% reservation for Indian women.

Despite of all these measures the participation of women in politics stills lags at a point. A fully fledged essence of democracy can be felt only if women are willing to participate in politics. But women fear to consider politics as their professional career. In the 71 years of Indian Independence we have witnessed a very few women in the political field. Woman is an instrument in the nation building process. Women should not only be provided with the provision for right to vote, but also power sharing, co-decision making, co policy making at all levels of governance. Although many women neglect to participate in the stream of politics, there are many women who took up politics and power as their mainstream. The feminist often urges women to achieve greater heights in life. They wanted women to succeed in all walks of life. But still there exists a gap between women when it comes under the name of politics. Although men mostly dominate in the political field there are also several women who stood and lived for a long period in this field.

According to the feminists, “History is the history of gender struggle”. From the independence period few women like Vijayalaxmi Pandit, Durga Bai Deshmukh, Kamala Nehru, Savithribai Phule, Indhira Gandhi served for the welfare of country and took politics in their hands. They stood against the male domination and were successful in their field. Now there are numerous women politicians in India. Sonia Gandhi, Sushma Swaraj, Meira Kumar, Mayawati, Mamta Bannerjee, Vasunthara Raje, Pratiba Patil, Brindha Karat, Smriti Irani, Menaka Gandhi, Jeyalalitha etc served as a role model that women can enter into politics and they can also firmly establish a successful political career. All these exceptional women politicians served as a cause for establishment of

women rights, women empowerment, upliftment of weak, social work and so on. They posed as a public figures in breaking the gender and cultural disparities that prevailed among women.

Statistical Facts

At present in Rajya Sabha, 31 women members are available out of total 244 members which is just 12.7% of the upper house. In Lok sabha only 66 women MP's are present out of 543 members which constitutes only 12.2%. As of October 2017 reports, 11 women serve as the Head of the State and 12 serve as Head of the Government. In total of 38 states, women account for less than 10% of the parliamentarians in single (or) lower houses as of June 2016.

Data reference from WWW. Mainstreamweekly.net : Women political participation- A catalyst for gender inequality in India.

Challenges for Women in Politics: In the struggle for gender justice political participation constitutes the first and foremost step in that direction. The holistic meaning of women empowerment can be realised only if women step their success in all the fields. As long as women taste the sweetness of success, there are also bitter challenges in all the fields. Politics too have many challenges and women face lots of problems in this field. The first and foremost challenge is the domestic responsibilities they are indulged with at home. The lack of family support, lack of financial clout, rising criminalisation in politics and the threat of character assassination fears women to enter in politics. Women's low self esteem and lack of confidence also falls under this category. Even if a woman becomes an MLA or MP women issues are not provided that much important in the parliament instead the departments like trade, foreign relations and economy are concentrated to the core. Due to these issues women feel psychologically and physically weak which reluctantly make them to accept that politics is man's world and they (women) have nothing to do in that.

Conclusion

The word empowerment means decentralisation of power and authority. It aims at getting participation of deprived sections of people in decision making process thus meaning giving voice to voiceless. Women of this century are energetic to prove themselves in the society. They are very much eager to prove to that they are no more inferior to men. But even today women restrict themselves in taking part in politics. As like all other fields' women should showcase their skills and abilities in politics. They are equal to men in politics too. Despite of all the challenges women should effectively take part in election. The true essence of democracy will be felt only if the women are allowed to influence the decision making process. Women's interest should be incorporated into the governance and this definitely leads to a holistic equality in our nation.

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